

Evaluating the Implementation of 5P's ... (Namatende, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10436641>

Evaluating the Implementation of 5P's Model in External Examinations of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Theses at Makerere University, Uganda

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Abstract

This study investigated the effectiveness of applying the 5P's model in the external examination of PhD theses at Makerere University, providing crucial insights into its functionality. Utilizing a case study design, the research aimed to evaluate whether Makerere's external examination system achieves its objectives, adheres to prescribed principles and follows systematic procedures. The study also sought to determine the involvement of relevant individuals and performance metrics in the University's external examination processes. Data collection involved vital personnel in the external examination processes, including academic deans, deputy vice-chancellors, college principals, deputy college principals, and PhD program coordinators, through in-depth interviews. The findings indicated that while the external examination of PhD theses at the University achieves its intended purpose and aligns with established principles, there is a noticeable absence of robust mechanisms for monitoring the performance of PhD students and external examiners, leading to persistent delays in submitting examination reports. In response to these findings, the study recommends establishing robust systems at Makerere University to monitor the performance and progress of external examiners and PhD students consistently. This proactive approach is envisioned to streamline the external examination process, ensuring timely submissions and cultivating a culture of excellence in academic progress.

Keywords: External examination, 5P's Model, PhD Theses, Makerere University, Performance management

Introduction

In the realm of higher education, external examination stands as a globally acknowledged cornerstone within quality assurance mechanisms, playing a pivotal role in upholding academic standards (Darojat, 2018). However, this recognition is juxtaposed with a paradox that questions the alignment between the confidence placed in external examinations and persistent apprehensions regarding academic standards (Fisher-Ari et al., 2017). This paradox is particularly pronounced in the discourse at Makerere University, where debates have emerged regarding the retention or removal of external examinations from the institution's quality assurance system (Betts et al., 2019). The impetus for this research arises from the escalating skepticism among Makerere University stakeholders concerning the efficacy and relevance of external examinations. In response to ongoing discussions within the academic corridors of Makerere, this study aims to unravel the complexities of the debate by investigating the application of Pryor, et al.'s 5P model in the external examinations of PhD theses.

External examination, rooted in history since the early nineteenth century, has evolved into a mechanism for universities to demonstrate the credibility of their academic standards, a sentiment echoed by Bloxham (Houston, 2018). In African universities, including Makerere, external examining is a longstanding practice with historical ties to affiliations with European universities during their inception (Kasozzi et al., 2019). Despite Makerere's century-old history of practicing external examination, challenges persist, with complaints about delayed completion of PhD theses due to late submission of reports from external examiners (Viana et al., 2022). Pryor's 5P's strategic management model, emphasizing Purpose, Principles,

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Processes, People, and Performance, emerges as a strategic tool for effective organizational operation (GÜLENC & KOZAK, 2016). This model is selected for its potential to align the process of external examinations at Makerere University with practical strategies and defined organizational purposes.

Framed within Pryor's 5P's model, this study delved into the Purpose, Principles, Processes, People, and Performance aspects of the external examination function at Makerere University. Despite external examination being a pillar of ensuring academic excellence at Makerere University, its process is marred by inadequacies, including delayed submission of examiners' reports and questionable practices. Stakeholders have raised concerns about the necessity of external examiners, leading to debates on the process's continued relevance (Kabeba, 2010; Ndyabahika, 2019). Within the framework of Pryor's 5P Model, this study aims to explore and address these challenges. The primary purpose of this study was to examine the application of Pryor's 5P's strategic management model in the external examination processes at Makerere University. The specific objectives included examining the extent to which the external examination system achieves its intended purpose, assessing adherence to set principles and processes, exploring the involvement of relevant people, and evaluating the use of performance measurement in the external examination of PhD theses at the University.

Numerous scholars have extensively explored the practice of external examination in higher education and its relevance in various contexts. Medland (2015) conducted a study in the UK assessing the effectiveness of the external examination system in upholding standards and instilling stakeholder confidence. Findings indicated a need to enhance professionalism, examiner calibration, and role clarity across UK universities. The study also emphasized the need for home institutions to support and recognize academic staff as external examiners. This investigation aims to determine if Makerere University supports and recognizes its academic staff undertaking external examinations. Unegbu and Ezeobi (2017) explored the role of external examiners in maintaining academic standards in Nigerian universities, emphasizing their significance in quality control and curriculum development. Despite the prioritization of external examiners' reports at Makerere University, it remains unclear if the University aligns its external examination processes with the 5Ps of strategic management. Hannan and Silver (2004) delved into why academics willingly engage in external examining despite time demands, citing reasons such as reciprocity and information gathering, even without significant support from their home institutions. While previous studies demonstrate the role of external examination in maintaining standards and information gathering, this investigation seeks to understand its application at Makerere University in Uganda.

Furthermore, Gold Smith's (2020) study on external examining procedures at the University of London emphasized the need to adhere to guidelines for appointing external examiners. However, how the nomination and appointment processes occur at Makerere University remains unknown, prompting the current study. Scholars like Silver (2006) and Finch (2011) have investigated external examining processes, highlighting institutional variations. The researcher aims to explore Makerere University's external examination processes, comparing them with existing practices and recommending improvements. Loukkola and Zhang (2010) emphasized the crucial role of individuals' quality and commitment in the success of external examination processes. This study will investigate how the people involved in external examining at Makerere University contribute to its effectiveness using the 5P's strategic model. Research on external examination and performance measurement in various contexts, such as Godo, Olel, and Oanda's (2011) study in Kenyan private universities, indicated improvements. However, there is a gap in understanding how performance measurement aligns with strategic management at Makerere University. Therefore, this investigation aims to apply Pryor White's 5Ps strategic model to assess external examination at Makerere University in Uganda.

At Makerere University, the role of external examination is deemed critical for maintaining and safeguarding academic excellence. However, the administration of this process is confronted with a multitude of deficiencies, most notably characterized by recurrent delays in the submission of examiners' reports. Eyangu et al. (2014) observed consistent delays in returning students' research projects at Makerere University Business School, sometimes accompanied by incomplete examination reports. Concerns have been raised regarding external examiners deviating from university guidelines, resulting in the production of reports deemed invalid and unreliable. The Rwendeire Report (2017) shed light on an inequitable examination process, both internal and external, contributing to the suboptimal assessment of graduate student work.

Consequently, substantial questioning has emerged among stakeholders regarding the necessity of external examiners at the University, with some advocating for eliminating external examinations for graduate dissertations and theses (Kabeba, 2010; Ndyabahika, 2019). By scrutinizing these challenges through the 5Ps strategic management model framework, it can be hypothesized that these issues may stem from deficiencies within the 5Ps, particularly as they pertain to the external examination function. In light of this hypothesis, the present study seeks to assess the extent to which Makerere's external examination system accomplishes its objectives, adheres to stipulated principles, and follows systematic procedures.

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Additionally, the study endeavored to ascertain the involvement of relevant individuals and the utilization of performance metrics in the University's external examination processes.

Objectives of the study

The study aimed to achieve the following research objectives:

1. Evaluate the extent to which Makerere University's external examination system fulfills its objectives.
2. Assess the degree of adherence of Makerere's external examination system to prescribed principles.
3. Investigate the implementation of systematic procedures in Makerere's external examination processes.
4. Determine the level of involvement of relevant individuals in the University's external examination procedures.
5. Examine the incorporation of performance metrics in Makerere University's external examination processes.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does Makerere University's external examination system achieve its objectives?
2. How well does Makerere's external examination system adhere to prescribed principles?
3. How are systematic procedures implemented in Makerere's external examination processes?
4. To what degree are relevant individuals involved in Makerere University's external examination procedures?
5. How are performance metrics incorporated into Makerere University's external examination processes?

Methodology

This qualitative inquiry, grounded in the interpretivist phenomenology of Edmund Husserl, delves into the utilization of Pryor et al.'s 5P model in overseeing the external examination of PhD theses at Makerere University. Informed by the belief that a profound understanding of a phenomenon emerges from those who have experienced it, interpretivism provides a fitting framework for unveiling the meaning inherent in the external examination experience. Aligning seamlessly with Husserl's transcendental argument, the epistemological stance views knowledge as socially constructed, guiding the research. Employing a case study design to test theoretical models, the study focuses on crucial university figures responsible for the external examination process. Data collection involves interviews and document reviews, utilizing thematic analysis to categorize responses based on the 5P model. The qualitative approach centers on a purposive sample of 18 participants strategically chosen to oversee the external examination process, applying thematic framework analysis to document reviews with Pryor et al.'s model as predetermined themes. Trustworthiness is ensured through face validity, engagement with supervisors for question clarification, and methodological rigor. Rigorous data analysis using ATLAS.ti v22 encompasses extraction, transcription, coding, and theme development, resulting in transparent reporting tied to study objectives. Ethical considerations prioritize consent, confidentiality, and anonymization. This comprehensive research methodology evaluated whether Makerere's external examination system achieves its objectives, adheres to prescribed principles, and follows systematic procedures. Drawing on key stakeholders' experiences, the detailed analysis and ethical considerations enhance the reliability and validity of the findings.

Results

Research Question 1

The first research question was: "To what extent does Makerere University's external examination system achieve its objectives?"

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Table 1: Views of Stakeholders on Whether the Management of External Examinations Achieves its Purpose

Theme Research questions	<i>Responses on Wheheer External Examination Achieves Purpose</i>	<i>Responses on Wetheheer External Examination Does Not Achieve Purpose</i>
To what extent does Makerere University's external examination system achieve its objectives?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The external examination is a direct quality assurance measure. • Achieving the intended purpose yields • auditing • It avoids the inbreeding of similar knowledge. • Certification of original work • Comparability of the programs in other universities • Education management and echo system • external examination gives a broader perspective on knowledge • Enables Judgement of good supervision • independent analytical feedback • independent opinions • knowledge transfer • opportunity for peer review • perspectives of different supervisors • Quality assurance checks for both the supervisor • standard assessment • a more comprehensive range of context 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No need for external examination at Makerere University • Makerere University has the capacity and does not need external examination. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unprofessionalism • Inadequate payment of external examiners • the quality of reports is questionable • Unfair judgment • Very Unfair assessment • Policies on external examination need urgent review •

As summarized in Table 1, the responses indicated a consensus among respondents that the management of external examination at Makerere University serves its purpose. Participants identified vital benefits, including its role as a quality assurance measure, independent review, avoidance of inbreeding of knowledge, and judgment of good supervision. Quotes from respondents emphasized the fundamental role of external examination in assessing both the supervisor and the student, providing independent opinions, and certifying the originality of work. The findings also highlighted the importance of external examination in maintaining comparability with programs in other universities, offering independent analytical feedback, and serving as a quality assurance check for both the supervisor and standard assessment.

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Research Question 2

How are systematic procedures implemented in Makerere's external examination processes?

Again, to answer these questions, key informants were posed this and other related questions. Some of their responses have been reported verbatim as follows:

Fairness and objectivity in the work are critical principles of external examination. Objectivity means that the external examiner should stick to the guidelines and mark the candidates' theses without bias. In that case, the external examiner should be mindful of who supervised the work of which the student wrote the theses. On the other hand, the principle of fairness requires the external examiner to be just and considerate when assessing any candidate's work. For that matter, the examiner should not malice a candidate (**Interviewee 003**).

Timeliness is yet another principle that must be observed while conducting external examinations. Timeliness means that the time taken to assess a candidate's work must be reasonable and should not extend to cause the candidate or supervisors of the candidate anxiety. However, in practice, some examiners violate this principle. Even the University policy of leaving examiners to work within three months violates this principle. It is worse if some examiners submit their examination reports beyond the stipulated time. I know of external examiners who often take over six months to return the students' theses and reports. This is disheartening (**Interviewee 007**).

For both students and EE, it is crucial. For example, some topics change very first. For example, current Law governing constantly has emerging issues or policies. When you submit the report to the EE, new trends, topics/themes will emerge. For example, I remember a student petitioning DRGT, saying they appointed an external examiner who had issues with the student. Unfortunately, the Research and Higher Degrees Committee did not know about the conflict (**Interviewee 004**).

One of the principles of external examination is transparency. This involves all the parties involved in external examination to handle the examination process openly and clearly. Indeed, transparency should be exercised at all levels of the external examination process. For example, the selection of the external examiner should be done as stipulated by policy. In practice, however, the choice of certain external examiners has been questioned or challenged because how some are chosen leaves much to be desired (**Interviewee 011**).

According to the researcher, an external examiner should not be a person who has been closely involved in the internal workings of the school, for example, teaching for the past three years. If somebody has been in the school, he or she cannot immediately become an external examiner. Suppose such a person is appointed as an external examiner. In that case, he or she may not exercise the freedom and independence so much desired to carry out his or her work suitably (**Interviewee 006**).

These results shed light on the adherence of Makerere University's external examination system to the principles outlined in Pryor's 5Ps model. Key informants emphasized the criticality of fairness and objectivity in external examination, underscoring the importance of unbiased assessment aligned with guidelines. The principle of timeliness emerged as a concern, with some examiners exceeding stipulated time frames, causing anxiety for both candidates and supervisors. The dynamic nature of particular disciplines, such as Law, highlighted the necessity for agility in the examination process. Transparency, a fundamental principle, was underscored as essential at all stages, including the selection of external examiners. Concerns were raised about the criteria for choosing external examiners, with suggestions to avoid individuals closely involved in the internal workings of the school for the past three years to ensure the desired freedom and independence in their role. These insights provide valuable perspectives on the strengths and challenges within the current external examination practices at Makerere University.

Research Question 3

How are systematic procedures implemented in Makerere University's external examination processes?

To answer this question, responses were collected through interviews, focusing on processes and challenges involved in external examination. Table 2 presents the responses, outlining various stages of the external examination process, including submitting a letter of intent by the student, nomination of examiners by the Dean and Deputy Principal, allocation of internal and external examiners, and approval by higher degree committees.

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Table 2: Responses on the Processes in the External Examination

No.	Research question	Responses/ data on processes involved in the external examination
01	To what degree do the processes involved in external examination at Makerere University align with the framework provided by Pryor's 5Ps strategic management model?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Once the student submits the letter of intent, the process begins. • Dean writes to the deputy principal to nominate the examiner. • For Makerere University, two internal examiners and one external examiner are appointed. • The Dean writes to the principal; in this case, the principal is the final person to appoint the examiners. • The CHUSS, the deputy principal, appoint the PhD. • DRGT is first copied in immediately when the college appoints an external examiner. • Dean writes to the deputy principal to nominate the examiner. • For Makerere University, they appoints two internal examiners and one external examiner. • The Dean writes to the principal; in this case, the principal is the final person to appoint the examiners. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stage I.- The first stage is for the student to complete their research an 2. Stage II - Consider the potential pool of examiners, choosing the person most suitable for doing the work dissertation. 3. Stage III - Selection of External Examiner: Involves some consideration from a pool of examiners, choosing the person more suitable for doing work. 4. Stage IV.- examination report. This results from the External Examiner instrument or reading the dissertation and assessing. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The department generates the need for the External Examiner. • After the nomination of the External Examiner, the names are taken to the higher degrees committee for approval. • The office of the Deputy Principal approves and appoints External Examiners after the committee's recommendation.

Interpreting the findings, the majority of respondents affirmed that Makerere University follows a sequential process for external examinations, emphasizing the need for approval at each stage. The first stage involves the student submitting a letter of intent, followed by the school board's research completion and the examiner's allocation. The process further includes the appointment of internal and external examiners, seeking approval from higher degree committees, and final approval by the Deputy Principal and Principal. Participants emphasized the importance of adherence to these steps to maintain the integrity of the external examination process.

Quotes from participants provided additional insights into the process, highlighting the role of the Directorate of DRGT upon the student's submission of a letter of intent and the initiation of the process when the student notifies the supervisor of readiness for examination. Some participants expressed the importance of considering a potential pool of examiners and the role of the Dean's office in communication.

While the study suggests that Makerere University generally adheres to external examination processes, it acknowledges process abuse, mainly due to issues such as poor remuneration leading to external examiners failing to submit reports. Additionally, the study points out that Makerere University does not conduct institutional induction for external examiners, contrasting with practices in other universities.

Research Question 4

What is the extent of involvement of key individuals in the university's external examination procedures?

A documentary review and interview revealed various university officers and groups, as illustrated in Figure 3, who manage external examinations for PhD theses at Makerere University.

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Table 3: Responses to Performance Measurements

Theme	Sub-themes	Responses	Sub-theme 1
Employment of performance measurements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ excel sheet to track progress ▪ appreciation letter by the deputy principal ▪ No systematic tracking mechanisms are in place for M&E ▪ keeping records ▪ monitoring and evaluation ▪ performance appraisal ▪ registrars sending reports and reminders ▪ sending score sheets ▪ CEDAT with follow-up tool ▪ a formal policy on issues of plagiarism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • • • • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting Policies • Tracking mechanism • Performance appraisal • Monitoring and evaluation

Table 3 categorizes the responses into themes and sub-themes, revealing that Makerere University employs various performance measurement methods. These include using Excel sheets to track progress, sending appreciation letters by Deputy Principals, and utilizing a follow-up tool in the College of Engineering, Design, Art, and Technology (CEDAT). However, a notable gap exists in the absence of systematic tracking mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation, and there is no formal policy addressing plagiarism issues.

The results indicate that Makerere University's performance measurement system for external examinations incorporates email communication, record-keeping, and performance appraisals. External examiners are motivated through appreciation letters. Nevertheless, the concerns of Deputy Principals and Deans underscore the need for increased recognition and remuneration for internal and external examiners. The study highlights the urgency of strengthening monitoring and tracking systems for all graduate programs, revising allowances for external examiners, and acknowledging the contributions of internal examiners.

Discussion of Findings

The outcomes derived from the external examination system at Makerere University agree with existing research in higher education. Medland's (2015) investigation in the United Kingdom (UK) accentuated the significance of augmenting professionalism, calibrating academic standards, and delineating roles in external examinations across universities (Medland, 2015). This parallels the current study's emphasis on the adherence to principles at Makerere University. Challenges delineated by Silver and Williams (1996), Gaunt (1999), and Sadler (2011) about national standards and comparability are resonant with the present study's exploration of adherence to principles, specifically Pryor's 5Ps model of strategic management. Difficulties identified in ensuring reliability in external examining, as articulated by Gaunt, mirror challenges identified in the current research, including process abuse and insufficient remuneration, causing delays and necessitating attention within the Makerere University context. Unegbu and Ezeobi's (2017) study on external examiners in Nigerian universities, emphasizing their role in maintaining academic standards and serving as impartial advisors, aligns with positive perceptions of external examination in the current study, substantiating a consistent theme of external examiners contributing to quality control and assurance. Hannan and Silver's (2004) examination of academics' willingness to serve as external examiners, despite competing demands, aligns with motivations suggested by the current study, emphasizing the value placed on reciprocity and information gathering, even in the absence of robust support from home institutions.

In response to the second research question, the examination of Makerere University's adherence to Pryor's 5Ps model for external examination unveils a substantial alignment between participant-perceived principles and official university documentation. As depicted in Figure 4.1, respondents recognize fundamental principles such as expertise, competence, excellence, professionalism, confidentiality, timeliness, and integrity as imperative in selecting external examiners. The scrutiny of Makerere University's graduate handbook reinforces these principles, accentuating external examiners' roles in evaluating instruments, student performance, and marking process reliability, aligning with Senate regulations. The literature review, citing further substantiates the positive impact of external examination practices in maintaining academic standards and ensuring educational quality and consistency. These findings align with the broader literature on external examining, including (Golden et al., 2020) emphasis on guidelines in appointing external examiners and the discourse on external examining practices in the UK and beyond, highlighting the diverse roles of external examiners. (Bloxxham & Boyd, 2012) exploration of the purpose of external examining aligns with the current study's focus on principles and standards, emphasizing

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the importance of appointing examiners from institutions known for defending academic standards, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of effective external examination practices.

The investigation into the alignment of external examination processes at Makerere University with Pryor's 5Ps strategic management model reveals a comprehensive and step-by-step approach to the external examination process. The study delineates various stages (Wray et al., 2018), such as the submission of a student's letter of intent, the nomination of examiners by the Dean and Deputy Principal, the assignment of internal and external examiners, and the approval by higher degree committees. The responses indicate a well-regulated and structured process at the University, underscoring the significance of strict adherence to maintain the integrity of the external examination process. The literature review complements these findings by providing insights into external examining practices in diverse international contexts, such as the US and the UK. While the study suggests overall adherence to external examination processes at Makerere University, it acknowledges challenges like process abuse, remuneration issues leading to delays, and the lack of institutional induction for external examiners. These challenges align with broader concerns in the literature about upholding academic standards and the necessity for clear guidelines and support for external examiners, highlighting the need for continuous improvement in the University's examination practices.

The research findings on the alignment between individuals involved in the external examination process at Makerere University and the people component of Pryor's 5Ps model reveal a complex landscape marked by conflicts, interference, and procedural delays. The study identifies various university officers and groups responsible for managing external examinations, as outlined in Figure 1, but notes discrepancies between the designated roles and the actual practices. Conflicts arise from the interference of some officers, such as principals, in appointing external examiners contrary to university policy. Prolonged committee meetings and contested choices for external examiners further contribute to delays in the examination process. Recommendations include reinforcing adherence to university policies, providing training for relevant personnel, and promoting timely student compliance with submission procedures. The literature review supplements these findings by emphasizing the crucial role of individuals, especially the quality of external examiners, in determining the success of the external examination process (Bloxham & Price, 2015). Studies from various contexts highlight the importance of organizational culture and effective management practices in universities, aligning with the challenges at Makerere University. The study extends the existing literature by applying Pryor's 5Ps model to assess the external examination process, providing a unique perspective on aligning people with strategic management components (Kapaanda & Benedict, 2019).

The research findings on Makerere University's external examination, analyzed through Pryor's 5Ps strategic management model, indicate a varied landscape of performance measurement practices. The University employs diverse methods, including Excel sheets, appreciation letters, and follow-up tools in specific departments. Notably, there is a lack of systematic tracking mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation, and a formal policy addressing plagiarism is absent. The results suggest a need for enhanced performance measurement practices, emphasizing robust monitoring and tracking systems for graduate programs. The literature review provides valuable context, with studies from various countries highlighting challenges and improvements in performance measurement in higher education (Al-Hosaini & Sofian, 2015). The findings underscore the importance of recognizing and remunerating examiners and suggest potential improvements in the broader university performance measurement system (Maeda & Socha-Dietrich, 2021). The study aligns with previous research emphasizing the need for balanced indicators and participatory-oriented monitoring mechanisms. Overall, it calls for Makerere University to strengthen its performance measurement practices for external examinations, drawing on insights from international experiences and addressing specific gaps identified within the institution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the examination of Makerere University's external examination aligns with prior research in higher education, emphasizing the importance of professionalism, academic standards calibration, and role clarity. The challenges identified, such as those related to national standards and comparability, echo broader discussions in the literature. The positive perceptions of external examination align with its recognized role in maintaining academic standards and serving as impartial advisors, as highlighted in studies from different contexts. The study's contribution lies in its contextualization within the 5Ps model, providing nuanced insights into the specific challenges and adherence to principles at Makerere University. The investigation enriches the existing literature, offering valuable perspectives on the intricacies of external examination practices and providing a foundation for continuous improvement.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings, Makerere University should continue reinforcing adherence to its policies and procedures, ensuring that external examination practices align with the principles outlined in Pryor's 5Ps model. Training relevant personnel involved in the external examination process could enhance clarity and efficiency. Additionally, measures to address conflicts and procedural delays, such as streamlining committee meetings and establishing transparent nomination processes, are essential for maintaining the integrity and timeliness of the external examination system. The University should consider instituting institutional inductions for external examiners and exploring mechanisms for addressing remuneration issues to mitigate delays. These recommendations aim to foster a more robust and effective external examination system at Makerere University.

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References

- Al-Hosaini, F. F., & Sofian, S. (2015). A review of balanced scorecard framework in higher education institution (HEIs). *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 5(1), 26-35.
- Betts, A., Chaara, I., Omata, N., & Sterck, O. (2019). Refugee economies in Uganda: what difference does the self-reliance model make? *Refugee Studies Centre*.
- Bloxham, S., & Boyd, P. (2012). Accountability in grading student work: Securing academic standards in a twenty-first century quality assurance context. *British Educational Research Journal*, 38(4), 615-634.
- Bloxham, S., & Price, M. (2015). External examining: Fit for purpose? *Studies in Higher Education*, 40(2), 195-211.
- Darojat, O. (2018). How are the results of quality assurance programs used to inform practices at a distance higher education? *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 19(1), 75-88.
- Fisher-Ari, T., Kavanagh, K. M., & Martin, A. (2017). Sisyphean neoliberal reforms: The intractable mythology of student growth and achievement master narratives within the testing and TFA era. *Journal of Education Policy*, 32(3), 255-280.
- Golden, J. W., Cline, C. R., Zeng, X., Garrison, A. R., Carey, B. D., Mucker, E. M., White, L. E., Shamblin, J. D., Brocato, R. L., & Liu, J. (2020). Human angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 transgenic mice infected with SARS-CoV-2 develop severe and fatal respiratory disease. *JCI insight*, 5(19).
- GÜLENC, S., & KOZAK, M. A. (2016). ASSESSMENT OF HEALTCARE HOSPITALITY GUIDE USING THE 5P'S MODEL. *International Journal of Health Management and Tourism*, 1(3), 37-45.
- Houston, G. (2018). *A study of the PhD examination: process, attributes and outcomes* University of Oxford].
- Kapaanda, L. N., & Benedict, O. H. (2019). Researching Together: Aligning Academic Employees with the Institution's Research Strategy. *African Educational Research Journal*, 7(4), 220-230.
- Kasozi, N., Tandlich, R., Fick, M., Kaiser, H., & Wilhelmi, B. (2019). Iron supplementation and management in aquaponic systems: A review. *Aquaculture Reports*, 15, 100221.
- Maeda, A., & Socha-Dietrich, K. (2021). Skills for the future health workforce: Preparing health professionals for people-centred care.
- Medland, E. (2015). Examining the assessment literacy of external examiners. *London Review of Education*, 13(3), 21-33.

Evaluating the Implementation of 5P's ... (Namatende, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10436641>

- Viana, R., Moyo, S., Amoako, D. G., Tegally, H., Scheepers, C., Althaus, C. L., Anyaneji, U. J., Bester, P. A., Boni, M. F., & Chand, M. (2022). Rapid epidemic expansion of the SARS-CoV-2 Omicron variant in southern Africa. *Nature*, 603(7902), 679-686.
- Wray, N. R., Ripke, S., Mattheisen, M., Trzaskowski, M., Byrne, E. M., Abdellaoui, A., Adams, M. J., Agerbo, E., Air, T. M., & Andlauer, T. M. (2018). Genome-wide association analyses identify 44 risk variants and refine the genetic architecture of major depression. *Nature genetics*, 50(5), 668-681.